

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

Foundational year

Nov 2018 - Oct 2019

	Preface
	Highlights
	Open Calls
	Infrastructure
	Research & outcomes
	Education & Community
	Financial
	Year 2

Preface

First and foremost, we are fortunate to be coordinating a very dedicated, enthusiastic and expert consortium of twenty-two partners, eleven public/eleven industry, who are steadfastly supporting the European research community in facilitating the introduction of 21st century research tools within an open science network, at scale. The EHDEN project is committed to success within the pillars of infrastructure, research, and community-building.

At the core of EHDEN is not data, technology or digital innovation per se, but collaboration. Key to success is the project consortium, but critical to EHDEN is enabling partnerships between those data centres who generate and use clinical data, those wishing to perform research on this data, and those who can enable this relationship. We believe that EHDEN can have a significant impact on patient care in Europe by enabling federated research on health data through standardisation of data and analytical pipelines.

We hope you enjoy reading this summary report of our year 1 progress and are very grateful you are on board for EHDEN's exciting and impactful journey.

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- Preface
- **Highlights**
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community
- Financial
- Year 2

Major achievements during year 1

We are proud of the project's progress in year one, and on behalf of the Consortium, thank everyone who has collaborated with us on our journey so far - it has been remarkable!

When we started EH DEN we were intent on ensuring we met our goals and deliverables as per plan, and importantly set a solid foundation for our collective work, as well as the future years of the project. As such, EH DEN has been very productive, hitting the ground running.

Open Calls

- **Processes** and **tools** for the open calls have been developed and implemented.
- An initial **pilot** call for Small/Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to be certified (11/28 selected) and Data Partner applicants (19/29 selected), with completion of certification of SMEs in December 2019, and initiation of the sub-grant agreement process with Data Partners in the same time interval.

Infrastructure

- Establishment of the EH DEN architecture, with advancement of the EH DEN Database **Catalogue**, data characterisation **tools** and **dashboards**.
- EH DEN and **OHDSI** are effectively symbiotic with reference to open source tooling and methods development. We made contributions to ETL and mapping tools, further developed the **ARACHNE** tool and advanced multiple analytical pipelines.
- Integrated **ELIXIR** authentication mechanisms.

Preface
Highlights
Open Calls
Infrastructure
Research & outcomes
Education & Community
Financial
Year 2

Major achievements during year 1

Education and Community

- The **EHDEN Academy** has been successfully supportive of the SME certification curriculum, effectively with user-testing by the selected SMEs, and will be launched publicly in early 2020.
- The OHDSI EU symposium was held in March 2019 linked significantly to EHDEN, especially with participating SMEs and potential applicant Data Partners.
- EHDEN and OHDSI **Communications teams** are working together on convergent activities to ensure aligned messaging.
- **Value propositions** have been developed for many key stakeholders and actors in this domain, with more to follow in year 2, and analysis of learning, especially with regards to sustainability of past and current projects/programmes has been initiated.
- EHDEN has **communicated extensively** via multiple channels, on and offline, inclusive of five webcasts, our website and social networks. The project has been presented at many conferences, workshops and meetings.
- The **Scientific** and **Ethics Advisory Boards** were formulated with nominations and first calls to articulate future work.

Major achievements during year 1

Preface

Highlights

Open Calls

Infrastructure

Research & outcomes

Education & Community

Financial

Year 2

Research and Outcomes:

- A first **study-a-thon** was held in December 2018, and resulted in an oral presentation, and media release, at EULAR 2019, followed by the publication of one of two manuscripts in The Lancet Rheumatology (the second has been submitted).
- Protocols for different **use cases**, e.g. Drug Utilisation, Drug Safety, HTA, have been developed and will be run on prior OMOP-mapped data, prior to working with EHDEN-mapped Data Partners.
- Methodological research in patient-level prediction and risk-stratified estimation has been presented at **conferences** and is being submitted for **publication**.
- Initial evaluation of the **ICHOM standards** for inclusion into the OMOP common data model has commenced.

THE LANCET
Rheumatology

ARTICLES | VOLUME 1, ISSUE 4, PE229-E236, DECEMBER 01, 2019

Opioid use, postoperative complications, and implant survival after unicompartmental versus total knee replacement: a population-based network study

Edward Burn, MSc * · James Weaver, MSc * · Daniel Morales, PhD · Albert Prats-Urbe, MPH · Antonella Delmestri, PhD · Victoria Y Strauss, PhD · Ying He, PhD · Danielle E Robinson, PhD · Rafael Pinedo-Villanueva, PhD · Spyros Kolovos, PhD · Talita Duarte-Salles, PhD · William Sprovierio, PhD · Dahai Yu, PhD · Michel Van Speybroeck, MSc · Ross Williams, MSc · Luis H John, MSc · Nigel Hughes, MSc · Anthony G Sena, BA · Ruth Costello, MSc · Belay Birtilie, MSc · David Culliford, PhD · Caroline O'Leary, MSc · Henry Morgan, PhD · Theresa Burkard, MSc · Prof Daniel Prieto-Alhambra, PhD · Patrick Ryan, PhD † · Show less · Show footnotes

Published: November 07, 2019 · DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2665-9913\(19\)30075-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2665-9913(19)30075-X) · Check for updates

- Preface
- Highlights**
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community
- Financial
- Year 2

Milestones & Deliverables

EHDEN has hit the ground running, meeting all major milestones on time, as anticipated. Three out of 21 deliverables were legitimately postponed and will be submitted in the second year:

- D 2.3 - OMOP CDM enhancements for Outcome-Driven Healthcare
- D 5.2 - Report on Quality Assurance and Control Procedures
- D 6.3 - Analysis of potential Public-Private Partnership exploitation models

Pilot call for SME training and certification

The first open call for SMEs in Europe to receive training and certification in the harmonisation of data took place during Q2 2019. This resulted to the first 11 SMEs being certified, covering 9 countries.

34 SME profiles made

28 Eligible applications

11 SMEs selected

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community
- Financial
- Year 2

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community
- Financial
- Year 2

The first open call for SMEs resulted in 11 EH DEN-certified SMEs. To allow Data partners to find an SME which suits their needs, we've created an online catalogue of Service Providers. This catalogue enables the user to search for specific service offerings, working languages, country, etc.

Find Listings

[Advanced Search](#)
Directory

- [OHDSI Software and Tools](#) (10)
- [OHDSI Training](#) (6)
- [OMOP CDM ETL](#) (11)
- [OMOP Standardized Vocabularies](#) (9)
- [Technical infrastructure services](#) (10)

Selected SMEs

- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stacc OÜ (EE) • edenceHealth NV (BE) • Easter-eggs (FR) • Biomeris (IT) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinerion Ltd (CH) • B2i Healthcare (HU) • ITTM S.A. (LU) • MediSapiens Ltd (FI) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P-95 (BE) • Imosphere (UK) • Quretec OÜ (EE) |
|--|---|--|

Pilot call for Data Partners - Process

The first open call for Data partners in Europe to receive funding for the harmonisation of their data took place during Q3 2019. We are currently going through the process of signing a sub-grant agreement with these data partners and anticipate that the first mappings will start during April 2020.

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community
- Financial
- Year 2

Pilot call for Data Partners - Outcome

This first pilot call for data partners has resulted in a selection of 19 data partners. Combined, these partners cover 8 countries and over 170 million patient records.

These patient records selected cover a wide diversity of data, including: Insurance/administrative claims, Outpatient electronic health records, Inpatient hospital electronic health records, Inpatient hospital billing systems, Registries and Biobanks.

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community
- Financial
- Year 2

The EHDEN Portal & Database Catalogue

Preface

Highlights

Open Calls

Infrastructure

Research
& outcomes

Education
& Community

Financial

Year 2

A first working version of the EHDEN portal is up and running. This portal will be the go-to place for all things EHDEN, unifying the Data Partner Catalogue, the federated analysis tools and the OHDSI tools. This platform also links to the EHDEN Academy and integrates the ELIXIR AAI security framework.

Currently, the Database Catalogue data sources are characterized based on a schema that can be easily defined by data partners based on the metadata attributes that best characterise their data. A first draft of the schema template was designed and is currently in place in the Database Catalogue.

A working test environment of this portal can be accessed via www.test.ehden.eu

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community
- Financial
- Year 2

Tool development

EHDEN and OHDSI are effectively symbiotic with reference to open source tooling and methods development. We have made significant contributions to many of the OHDSI tools and also helped to develop some of them *de novo*.

A unified interface for the OHDSI tools.

Allows distribution and browsing of all standardised vocabularies in the OMOP CDM.

The ETL tooling support the SMEs and Data Partners to create the transformation scripts.

Online repository of over 200 pre-defined study queries.

Technical solution for the federated network in EHDEN.

Online tool which allows comparison of two vocabulary versions.

Authentication mechanism from the ELIXIR project being used for single user sign on into EHDEN.

Dashboard development

Preface

Highlights

Open Calls

Infrastructure

Research & outcomes

Education & Community

Financial

Year 2

The Data Quality Dashboard (DQD) provides a comprehensive, customisable, and transparent way to both evaluate and communicate the quality of an OMOP CDM instance. It provides both the code to run data quality checks against an OMOP CDM instance, as well as visualising the results in a web application. The data quality checks were organised using the widely accepted Kahn Framework for data quality. This groups the checks types in categories: Conformance, Completeness and Plausibility.

Each SME and data partner will be expected to run the Data Quality Dashboard on the data at their site once it is converted to the OMOP CDM. We believe the DQD is a strong foundation for data quality reporting, and a key tool to ensure confidence in the evidence generated through the EH DEN federated network.

RESULTS

SYNTHEA SYNTHETIC HEALTH DATABASE

Results generated at 2019-08-22 14:15:06 in 29 mins

Show entries

Column visibility CSV

Search:

	STATUS	CONTEXT	CATEGORY	SUBCATEGORY	LEVEL	DESCRIPTION	% RECORDS
	FAIL						
+	FAIL	Validation	Completeness	None	TABLE	The number and percent of persons in the CDM that do not have at least one record in the VISIT_OCCURRENCE table. (Threshold=0%).	66.96%
+	FAIL	Verification	Completeness	None	FIELD	The number and percent of distinct source values in the race_source_value field of the PERSON table mapped to 0. (Threshold=0%).	50.00%
+	FAIL	Verification	Conformance	Relational	FIELD	The number and percent of records that have a value in the person_id field in the OBSERVATION_PERIOD table that does not exist in the PERSON table. (Threshold=0%).	49.58%
+	FAIL	Verification	Plausibility	Atemporal	FIELD	The number and percent of records with a value in the gap_days field of the DRUG_ERA table less than 0. (Threshold=0%).	24.07%
+	FAIL	Verification	Completeness	None	FIELD	The number and percent of records with a value of 0 in the standard concept field race_concept_id in the PERSON table. (Threshold=0%).	16.74%

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes**
- Education & Community
- Financial
- Year 2

Use Cases

The initial use cases agreed upon by the EH DEN partners to date are drug utilisation studies (Use Case 1), regulatory research into the safety of drugs and devices (Use Case 2) and health technology assessments (HTA, Use Case 3).

Protocols for these different use cases have been developed and were submitted to data access committees of prior OMOP-mapped data sources. This allows us to develop analytical pipelines and to drive tool and dashboard development prior to working with EH DEN-mapped Data Partners.

**Drug
Utilisation**

**Drug & Device
Safety**

HTA

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes**
- Education & Community
- Financial
- Year 2

Study-a-thon

A first Study-a-thon was held in December 2018 at Oxford University, bringing together around 40 stakeholders with various backgrounds. This Study-a-thon compared the safety of two types of medical devices for knee replacement surgery, namely partial vs total knee replacement, and as such was a substantial contribution to Use Case 2.

During this 5-day meeting, we were able to go from question, to cohort characterisation, to data analysis and ultimately to evidence generation. Therefore, the Study-a-thon is a brilliant example of what EH DEN aims to achieve: Reduce the time to go from question to getting an answer for the benefit of patients.

This first Study-a-thon resulted in an oral presentation and media release at EULAR 2019, followed by the publication of one of two manuscripts in The Lancet Rheumatology (Annex 1) and the second one being submitted.

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes**
- Education & Community
- Financial
- Year 2

ICHOM Standard sets

An ICHOM standard set encompasses standardised outcomes, measurement tools, time points and risk adjustment factors for a given condition.

Due to the time investment required for extending the OMOP CDM with an ICHOM standard set, we have for the time being selected the COPD/Asthma, prostate cancer and inflammatory arthritis standard sets. These sets were selected following consultation with the whole consortium and drive development of dashboards in EH DEN.

COPD
Asthma

Prostate Cancer

Inflammatory
Arthritis

The EHDEN Academy has been developed during Q2 of 2019 in collaboration with OHDSI. Ninety users across 11 SMEs and our own EHDEN partners have tested and taken the 6 courses currently in the Academy (Cfr. below). More courses will be developed during 2020 and we anticipate making the Academy publicly available during Q1 2020.

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community**
- Financial
- Year 2

EHDEN Academy

ETL

Participants

Badges

Grades

Welcome

Introduction

ETL - Step 1

ETL - Step 2

ETL - Step 3

ETL - Step 4

Examining

Course Feedback

Dashboard

Extract, Transform and Load

Dashboard / My courses / ETL

0 ENROLLED STUDENTS

0 STUDENTS COMPLETED

0 IN PROGRESS

0 YET TO START

Welcome

EHDEN
EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

EHDEN Foundation

Extract, Transform and Load

OHDSI
OHDSI-in-a-Box Virtual Machine

aws

OHDSI
OHDSI

OMOP CDM and Standardised Voc...

Academy Support

Infrastructure

Course Introduction

Announcements

ETL Forum

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community**
- Financial
- Year 2

Communication - Channels

Harmonising 100 million patient records poses a socio-technical problem rather than a technical problem alone. While EHDEN aims to build the infrastructure necessary to enable generating outcomes from real-world data at scale, a large part of the success will also depend on creating a self-sustaining community, inclusive of all stakeholders (data partners, SMEs, regulators, payers, researchers, patients, ...).

Besides the heavy focus on creating this community via many different external channels, we have also set up many different internal communication channels to ensure that the project runs smoothly.

Internal Channels

- EHDEN Forum
- ExCom meeting (monthly)
- EHDEN SharePoint
- EFPIA meeting (bi-weekly)
- Mailing lists
- WP meetings (weekly)
- General Assembly meeting (2/year)
- Advisory board meetings (2/year)

External Channels

6403 Visitors

142 Subscribers

420 Followers

213 Followers

29 Subscribers

The EHDEN website is a central hub for all our communication activities. It's currently the place which holds all news and information on the project and where people can find information about, and apply to the open calls. The EHDEN platform, SME and Data catalogue, Academy, etc., will all become accessible via the EHDEN website. With 8755 visitors during the first year, of which about 80% are unique visitors, the website can be considered a huge succes.

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community
- Financial
- Year 2

- 8755** Visitors
- 71731** Page views
- 2.55%** Bounce rate

Homepage	34 %
Data Partner call	7 %
Vision & Mission	5 %
Consortium Partners	5 %
SME call	4 %

Communication & Dissemination activities

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community**
- Financial
- Year 2

4 Publications
(Cfr. Annex 1)

46 Oral
Presentations

13 Poster
Presentations

8 Workshops

16 News articles

58 Tweets

39 Posts

1 EHDEN movie

5 Webinars

2 Newsletters

2 Media releases

17 Media
activities

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community**
- Financial
- Year 2

Value Propositions

The three priority stakeholders agreed upon by the EH DEN Consortium are small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs), data sources and regulatory/HTA/payer agencies. These Value Propo- sitions are used as guidelines when reaching out to these different stakeholders and they will be continously refined based on user feedback. For example, the SME and Data Partner value propositions have been used in the call descriptions of the initial open calls.

During the second year, we will target the pharmaceutical industry and patients/patient representatives as the next stakeholder groups.

Small and medium-sized enterprises

Data Partners

Regulatory, HTA & payer agencies

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- **Education & Community**
- Financial
- Year 2

Sustainability - Landscape

Sustainability in a project like EHDEN needs to be addressed from the beginning. During the first year of the project, initial discussions were held, including a specific workshop during the 2nd General Assembly Meeting. We are now organising a 2-day meeting early in the 2nd year, solely focussed on defining EHDEN's sustainability.

In order to guide the development of a first sustainability scenario an analysis of other public-private partnerships and initiatives is being organised. For this, an input template has been created in order to get information from known projects and/or initiatives that could inspire the sustainability of EHDEN.

PPP Summary
QUALIFIERS (short description)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation/competitive advantage: • Cooperation/collaboration/organisation: • Disease focus: • Role of data/databases: • Role of open source/open innovation:
CHARACTERISTICS (sections will be completed according to information available)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product/service(s): • Who pays for the products/services: • Who provides the products/services: • Value proposition: • Organisational structure: • Revenue streams:. • Costs/budget:

Advisory Boards & Committees

EHDEN currently has 2 advisory boards and 2 committees up and running. Members for these boards were suggested by the consortium and had to sign an agreement to become part of the respective boards. The Data source prioritisation and SME certification committees have contributed to the success of the first open calls for SMEs and for Data Partners. Discussions with and guidance from the scientific and ethical advisory board are expected to ramp up from year 2 onwards.

	Internal members	External members
Scientific Advisory Board	/	
Ethical Advisory Board	/	
Data Source Prioritisation Committee		
SME Certification Committee		

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- **Education & Community**
- Financial
- Year 2

- Preface
- Highlights
- Open Calls
- Infrastructure
- Research & outcomes
- Education & Community
- Financial**
- Year 2

Harmonisation fund - Current status

Currently remaining funds

The EHDEN Harmonisation fund has a total of 17 000 000 € available. In our first open call, we've granted 1 650 000 €, which means that we've currently earmarked just under 10% of the total funds available.

Grant size distribution

Nineteen applications were successful in the first open call for Data Partners. Sixteen applications will create a completely new mapping while 3 applications requested to revise an already existing mapping.

Combined, these 19 applications requested 1 650 000 €, with a grant size distribution as indicated.

	Preface
	Highlights
	Open Calls
	Infrastructure
	Research & outcomes
	Education & Community
	Financial
	Year 2

Looking ahead to year 2

Based on this initial year's output, we are confident that in the second year we will see the first mapping cycle work between Data Partners and certified SMEs, which will form the basis for the progenitor EHDEN network. We look forward to working together with Data Partners on use cases to validate and verify the network approach later in 2020, evaluate the platform architecture, and meanwhile, expanding our open calls to more Data Partners and SMEs.

We hope to see greater collaboration with our sister BD4BO projects, as well as other non-IMI projects and institutions on convergent goals in 2020, as well as the expansion of our symbiosis with OHDSI. In January we will host our second study-a-thon, looking forward to building on the tremendous success of the first.

It is in all our interest to see progress in generating evidence at scale, with speed and still with quality, and ultimately impacting on outcomes for EU citizens and patients. We hope that our first year has been instrumental in assisting us in reaching this destination.

Peter Rijnbeek
Nigel Hughes

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

The European Health Data & Evidence Network has received funding from the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 806968. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and EFPIA.

Annex 1 - Publications

Annex 1

THE LANCET
Rheumatology

ARTICLES | VOLUME 1, ISSUE 4, PE229-E236, DECEMBER 01, 2019

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[Patrick Ryan, PhD](#) † • [Show less](#) • [Show footnotes](#)

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Annex 1 - Publications

Annex 1

ELSEVIER

Journal of Biomedical Informatics

Volume 93, May 2019, 103154

Patient data discovery platforms as enablers of biomedical and translational research: A systematic review

Alina Trifan

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1532046419300723?via%3Dihub>

Annex 1 - Publications

Annex 1

<https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/>

Annex 1 - Publications

Annex 1

DISSERTATIONES
INFORMATICAE
UNIVERSITATIS
TARTUENSIS
12

<https://dspace.ut.ee/handle/10062/64628>